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**AN ASSESSMENT:
NUSSBAUM'S CAPABILITIES APPROACH
AS A THEORY OF SOCIAL JUSTICE**

Submission for a course in Ethical Issues in Public Policy

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Abstract

Martha C. Nussbaum, in her book *Creating Capabilities- the Human Development Approach*, describes her capabilities approach as both a theory of justice and a theory of welfare. In describing and critically reviewing the main arguments of Nussbaum's approach, this paper attempts to answer the question: to what extent is the capabilities theory a theory of social justice? The main ideas under discussion are those presented in the core chapter of the book (chapter two); however, her ideas on global justice and political structures as presented in other chapters have also been referenced.

The paper briefly explores the concept of social justice as presented by John Rawls and David Miller, and selectively applies the main arguments in the assessment of Nussbaum's approach. A theory of social justice, the paper observes, should provide for both distributive justice and procedural justice. In examining how the two types of justice are applied, or should be applied, in the context of the capabilities approach, reference is also made to ideas presented by Thomas Pogge and Ingrid Robeyns.

The paper reveals the strengths and limitation of Nussbaum's capabilities theory as a theory of social justice. It further gives recommendations on how the limitations could be addressed to secure social justice; both at the national and global level.

Table of Content

Abstract	1
Table of Content	2
Nussbaum’s Capability Approach	3
What is Social Justice?	5
Capability Approach as a Theory of Justice	6
Distributive Justice.....	6
On Equality and Equity	6
On Outcomes.....	9
Beyond the Threshold	11
On Global Justice	13
Procedural Justice	16
Beyond the benevolent dictator	16
A Just Decision.....	17
Conclusion	18
Bibliography.....	19
Core reference	19
Further reference	19

Nussbaum's Capability Approach

Martha Nussbaum makes an argument for social justice as equality in human dignity. This dignity, she argues, can only be safeguarded if everyone enjoys ten central capabilities, at least at a minimum threshold.

Nussbaum asserts that to understand what capabilities are, one has to begin with the question: what are people actually able to do and to be? This, she would argue, should not be confused with the question: what are people doing and being? Capabilities are, thus, essentially opportunities to do and to be, and not the action of doing or being in itself.

She emphasises that capabilities should be understood as freedoms where individuals have the choice of whether or not to utilize the available capabilities. Freedom, she argues, has intrinsic value. If an individual chooses to realise the freedoms, then it is said that such freedoms or capabilities have been converted to functionings. Nussbaum argues that governments should not focus on ensuring functionalities but rather on providing capabilities. Accordingly, no individual should be forced to convert available capabilities to functionings.

In clarifying what capabilities entails, Nussbaum calls for an understanding of capabilities as combined capabilities where internal capabilities are coupled with external capabilities- made up of the social, economic and political environment. The social environment entails social norms and culture; economic environment entails the economic policies and opportunities accruing from such policies; and the political environment entails the political institutions and political culture.

When one of the components of the combined capabilities is unfulfilled then such freedoms are curtailed as it would be impossible to optimally convert the capabilities to functionings. For instance, if one has the ability to express political opinion but the freedom of political expression is curtailed in the prevailing political system then the capability of political expression cannot be converted to a functioning.

Nussbaum argues that internal capabilities are fluid and are shaped by society through education and health among other practices, right from birth. It follows that a society can constrain capabilities by not facilitating the development of internal capabilities. The society, therefore, has the responsibility of securing both internal and external capabilities.

Nussbaum describes her conception of capabilities as a foundation of social justice. She argues for a threshold of the combined capabilities, to which every individual is entitled. She

consequently advocates for treatment of all people with equal respect; every individual in essence is eligible for equal dignity.

Ten capabilities are pointed out as the central capabilities, which every just society should inspire to provide to all its citizens at a specified minimum threshold. Applying the principle of political liberalism, she argues that the threshold-setting should be a national decision based on historical and cultural considerations.

The determination of the central capabilities, Nussbaum argues, should not be left for decision through political process since they are so essential for a worthy life. They are based, she asserts, on sound argument and recognized world consensus. The central capabilities, according to Nussbaum, are: life; bodily health; bodily integrity; sense, imagination, and thought; emotions; practical reasoning; affiliation; other species; play; and control over one's environment.

Nussbaum asserts that the central capabilities are not hierarchical; all of them need to be pursued at the set minimum threshold for every individual. In case of competing capabilities, she argues for a tragic choice where one of the competing capabilities can be preferred over another on a case by case basis depending on the outcome of the pursuing one capability over another. Such tragic choices, she argues, should be addressed and avoided since all of the central capabilities are essential.

Nussbaum stresses the role of political institutions in the enforcement of the central capabilities. She argues that capabilities should be adopted as political entitlements and provided for in constitutions. In the interpretation and implementation of the central capabilities, and oversight of the implementation, she calls for just and democratic political procedures and structures.

What is Social Justice?

Social justice might mean different things to different people. Terms that have been used to describe the principles of social justice include equality, equity, needs, liberty, and respect¹. I believe that it is important to explore the term and construct a concept to be applied in the assessment of Nussbaum's capabilities approach as a theory of social justice. I will adapt social justice as conceived by John Rawls and David Miller².

Rawls argues for justice as fairness and asserts that social justice's essence is to protect equal access to basic liberties, and opportunities for citizens. He emphasizes that the least advantaged in society should be treated fairly. Rawls argues for equal basic liberties, but holds that social and economic inequality is justified as long as these inequalities are: to the greatest benefit of the most disadvantaged; or associated with positions that are open to everyone by equal opportunity. In coming up with the conception of justice as liberties and duties to be assigned to political institutions and individuals, he applies the contract theory where individuals (detached from individual bias) cooperate in the construction of principles of justice to be applied by the society.

According to Miller, social justice has to do with the distribution of societal advantages and disadvantages. He asserts that the value of the benefits to be assigned should be established by the relevant population as a whole. He prefers an understanding of social justice as what is agreed by a society before knowing individual stakes in the decision. As such, he argues that social justice must not be a rationalization of individual interests. Miller's theory is pegged on three principles of social justice: need, desert, and equality. Respectively, a just society would be one where: (1) no one is lacking basic necessities essential for functioning; (2) distribution of benefits is based on performance; and (3) every citizen is treated equally. Inequality is justified if it motivates people to strive and/or if it results from the principle of desert.

This paper will take a conception of social justice that incorporates two aspects of justice brought out by Rawls and Miller: distributive justice and procedural justice. Distributive justice answers the question of how rights and opportunities are allocated in society, while procedural justice looks at how the decisions- in the establishment of societal values- are made.

Capability Approach as a Theory of Justice

Nussbaum has described her capability approach as a theory of justice and, in admitting to one of its limitations³, she describes it as a partial theory of social justice. This section critically reviews the arguments for the approach as a theory of justice. The concept of justice, I argue, is one that is based on fairness and equality in distribution and procedure.

Distributive Justice

On Equality and Equity

Nussbaum's capabilities approach is based on the individual as the end, with each individual entitled to a minimum threshold of central capabilities without which life would not be worth of dignity. This is based on the premise that every individual is entitled to equal dignity.

Nussbaum believes that everyone should have access to the central freedoms regardless of the gender, age, social and economic class, religious beliefs, political opinion, among other divisions that could be manipulated for marginalization. Every individual is, hence, entitled to both internal capabilities and external capabilities that would allow for corresponding central functionings.

Equal dignity in choice and ability to choose, which is at the heart of Nussbaum's approach, I argue, is a foundation for a socially just society. What is exceptional about this approach is that it does not attach central opportunities to merit, position, potential for striving, or obligation accruing for being part of a society. Every person is entitled to a life worth of dignity by virtue of being human.

Nussbaum does not give central focus on equity in her arguments. She, however, holds that in a situation of differential treatment involving an innately skilled individual and another individual lacking such skills, she would prefer better treatment to the latter. Although Nussbaum believes that basic capabilities should be equally nurtured, she argues that individuals with cognitive disabilities require more assistance to develop the central capabilities necessary to strive. The limited scope of equity in the distribution of the central capabilities, I argue, is a limitation to Nussbaum's capabilities approach. For distribution of societal values to be fair, I argue, a broader and more inclusive conception of equity needs to be embraced.

Adapting Sens' concept of conversion factors⁴, Robeyns lists three conversion factors essential for capabilities to be converted to functionings: personal conversion factors, social conversion factors, and environmental conversion factors. Although these conversion factors appear to be similar to what Nussbaum refers to as combined capabilities, they broaden the view on what could hinder equal access to capabilities. Robeyns' personal conversion factors, for instance, also include characteristics that innately differentiate one person from another such as intelligence and sex. The social conversion factors resemble Nussbaum's capabilities accruing from the social, economic, and political environment. Robeyns introduces the environmental conversion factors as those that include geographical location and climate. These additional considerations (environmental conversion factors and innate abilities), I argue, need to be adequately addressed to allow for a better understanding of the capabilities available to every individual.

Nussbaum argues that internal capabilities are fluid elements of a person and that they are "not hard-wired into our DNA"⁵. Although she implicitly admits to the possibility of innate skills, she holds that the development of basic skills is determined by external factors. However, it should be noted that there are innate personal characteristics that affect the level and speed at which personal capabilities are developed. This would explain why two students in the same class with the same dream career, level of motivation, effort, education, and teachers' attention might not achieve the same level of success in their pursuit.

I hold that in the nurturing of internal capabilities, more attention should be given to individuals with lower innate abilities. More teaching attention should be given to those with difficulty in understanding basic concepts and more physical health care should be availed for those with physical disability or difficulty. In addition, I believe, those who live in disadvantageous climatic and geographical conditions require additional attention to overcome such disadvantage and enjoy equal opportunity. For instance, people living in earth-quake prone areas or regions experiencing severe consequences of climate change might fail to strive as they would otherwise have because of fear or deteriorating opportunities, respectively. In such cases, a socially just society would concentrate on disaster management mechanisms that would settle fear and ensure sustainable availability of capabilities.

Nussbaum's capability approach, I argue, also fails to address past social injustices. For a society to transition from an unjust one to one that embraces justice as set out by the

capability approach, it would have to ensure that the disadvantages accrued by the marginalized individuals are first offset. Individuals are in many situations marginalized due to their association with a particular gender, religion, race, and/or ethnicity among other affiliations. In such situations group rights could be assigned to the extent that it offsets disadvantages that would hinder equal opportunity. For instance, an ethnic group that had previously been denied educational and economic opportunity, might require a quota for such opportunities for its members to enjoy similar opportunities as other citizens. If another community was previously deprived of property rights in the form of communal land, such rights would need to be assigned as group rights. Nussbaum dismisses group rights although admitting, in passing, to the benefits of affirmation action when directed towards creating individual capabilities. She fails to acknowledge the great potential of group rights in addressing past injustices and assisting societies to come to a full realization of equal capabilities.

I argue that group rights should be a central consideration for transitioning societies to reduce the disadvantages of the marginalized groups to a level that would avail them equal capabilities. Such group rights, I assert, should be assigned equitably within the group. Some individuals within the previously-marginalized groups might have been more marginalized than others hence the need to pay attention to different needs even within the groups.

I argue for what I call negative equity⁶, where the disadvantaged in the society are treated better and proportionately to their disadvantages to the level where equal dignity can be enjoyed as the minimum threshold of the central capabilities. This is in contrast to positive equity⁷ where more attention and capabilities would be awarded to those who are innately skilled and with more internal capabilities. Although Miller argues for desert as one of the principles of justice, I agree with Nussbaum in asserting that such positive equity could be detrimental to equal dignity; especially if applied below the threshold level. In addressing the problem of competing principles of justice, needs and desert, Miller asserts that in some situations desert could be chosen over needs where those in need are not deserving. Can a society that distributes the central capabilities based on merits qualify as a socially just one? In the final analysis, I argue, that a balanced application of both equality and equity in the achievement of equal dignity at the minimum threshold is crucial.

On Outcomes

Nussbaum's capability approach is based on securing capabilities as freedoms and not functionings. She asserts that a just society should not require its citizens to realize capabilities but rather should ensure the availability of such capabilities to its citizens. It follows that the citizens would then have the freedom consider which capabilities to pursue, if any at all. She, however, admits that functionings are the end to striving for capabilities since capabilities would not be useful if they are never utilized. She even notes that if internal capabilities are not realized, they could be lost. Although Nussbaum acknowledges the importance of functionings, she fails to acknowledge the flip side; where functionings or the outcomes of the capabilities could be detrimental to equal dignity.

Imagine that one part of a population decides not to seek medical health care because its members' religious beliefs do not support practice of scientific medicine. Nussbaum might argue that the individuals are enjoying equal dignity by having the choice of not seeking medical care as long as that option is open for them. A closer look at the outcome of this freedom will reveal the importance of considering whether the outcomes of capabilities are just. The individuals, belonging to this particular religious group, who choose not to realise the functionality of bodily health might consequently not be able to live a normal length of human life due to body ailments that could have otherwise been treated using modern medicine. This would be in contrast to other parts of the population where individuals are healthy and have a considerably higher life expectancy. The unrestricted freedoms on central capabilities, I argue, could translate to life choices that contradict equal dignity.

What if this population does not also believe in modern education and participation in political process? Individuals in this population might not develop internal capabilities necessary for a rational conversion of the central capabilities to functionalities; this is particularly detrimental to the capability of practical reasoning. The same individuals would also not have the ability to control their environment, or to choose to do so, by influencing societal decision making that would affect their lives. As Nussbaum notes on the loss of capabilities if not realized, these individuals would lose the internal capabilities associated with realizing other central capabilities not supported by their religion.

I argue that a society cannot boast of securing equal dignity if some parts of its population do not realize the most central capabilities even if they are made available to all citizens. As illustrated above, the realm of central freedoms can turn into a vicious cycle of incapacities that might affect one part of society more than the rest. This would visibly translate to

societal inequality in the ability to realise lives worth of dignity. I agree with Nussbaum's rationale for having capabilities as individual freedoms, to cater for the diversity and to enable striving. I, however, argue that for the central capabilities to translate to a life of equal dignity, the minimum thresholds for the most central capabilities need to be guaranteed as functionalities.

When addressing the issue to tragic choice, Nussbaum admits that although there is no hierarchy in the list of central capabilities, it is possible to advance one capability over another depending on the outcome. In adapting Wolff's and De-Shalit's concepts of fertile functioning and corrosive disadvantage, Nussbaum argues that in a tragic choice situation priority should be given those central capabilities that have the effect of enhancing other capabilities. I argue that the same logic should be applied in determining which central capabilities should be enforced as functionalities at the minimum threshold level. I assert that those capabilities which have corrosive disadvantage if not realized should take precedence in this case. This, I argue, is because if such capabilities are not secured, their absence would make one or more of the other capabilities inaccessible hence having the potential of reducing the dignity of life. Capabilities with fertile functioning, on the other hand, can only enhance other capabilities hence do not negatively affect the dignity of life set as the minimum threshold of central capabilities.

I also argue that in considering which capabilities should be enforced as functionings, the issue of individual responsibility in upholding equal dignity needs to be addressed. Nussbaum notes that an individual should not be given the freedom of being treated disrespectfully. I argue, that an individual should also not be given the choice of treating others disrespectfully. This, therefore calls, for the need to require functionality in the form of individual responsibility in upholding equal dignity.

Beyond the Threshold

Nussbaum is very clear on how equal dignity should be enforced to the minimum threshold of the central capabilities. She, however, does not give clear direction on how the principle of equal dignity can be applied in the distribution questions beyond the threshold level.

Nussbaum, nonetheless, gives examples where unequal distribution beyond the minimum threshold would translate to unequal dignity to some individuals or groups in a society. The distribution of voting rights and religious freedoms, for instance, would result in unequal dignity if some groups get more voting quota or number of days of worship compared to other groups. Other central capabilities such as bodily health if availed to one group more than another, even if both groups attain the minimum threshold, would hurt the dignity of the disfavoured group. Nussbaum admits to the difficulty of determining how unequal distribution of material conditions would affect human dignity.

I agree with Nussbaum's assessment that discriminatory allocation of capabilities might warrant equal distribution even beyond the threshold. This, I argue, should hold for both political entitlements and material conditions. It would not be correct to call a society just if it provides better housing to those belonging to the leader's ethnic group even though the socially accepted minimum housing is availed to everyone.

Beyond the threshold, I argue, positive equity could be applied. In which case, individuals who realize available capabilities by converting them to functionings are afforded more capabilities. I propose a desert system where benefits are gained as a result of achieved outcomes; such benefits should be limited to material conditions. As illustrated above, unequal distribution of political entitlements, even through a fair merit system, would be detrimental to equal dignity. If an individual pursues a musical career by choosing to realize the central capabilities essential for the development of her/his musical skills, such skills should be rewarded by provision of capabilities for further development of such skills. In this instance, this could mean those with superior musical skills be rewarded by scholarships to an advanced music school. Although this reward system would produce elites⁸ in the various career spaces in society, I argue that this distribution of capabilities is fair as long as everyone has the central capabilities to start with and hence equal chances of attaining the elite status. This system would work as long as the equal minimum threshold is not jeopardized for the benefit of the elites.

In another scenario, I argue that a business woman who extensively utilizes the available central capabilities to set up a flourishing business, should benefit from more profits than her counterparts who were unable to reach the same level of achievement given the same central capacities. However, should this business woman be allowed to have monopoly power if she uses her profits to grow her business into a billion-dollar empire with unmatched capacities to compete in a particular market niche?

The questions we must ask in attempting to address distribution issues beyond the threshold are: (1) whether the equal minimum threshold is enough, and (2) to what degree socio-economic inequality should be acceptable beyond the threshold. In some situations the minimum threshold might not seem enough if the difference between capabilities at the threshold and those enjoyed by the elite is enormous. In such situations, I argue, a society should increase the minimum threshold to reduce this capability gap⁹. I argue that these questions should be constantly reflected upon by societies aspiring for social justice, and adjustments on the threshold enforced accordingly. In doing so, I assert, any new threshold should not be set lower than the preceding threshold as this would be synonymous to reducing the human dignity required at minimum. However, if a threshold reduction is crucial for equality at the threshold to be sustained, for fairness, such a reduction should be accompanied by an equivalent reduction of capabilities that would have been availed as desert.

On Global Justice

Nussbaum argues that the central capabilities are so critical that they entail human entitlement. This argument denotes the global nature of such capabilities. Nussbaum struggles with the question of whether the minimum threshold of enforced capabilities should be the same for every country. While she believes that every country should set its own threshold in consideration of history and traditions, she acknowledges the different economic endowments that would come to play in setting such a threshold. A country in sub-Saharan Africa, for instance, would most likely set a lower threshold than a country in Western Europe. As Nussbaum recommended, the threshold should be aspirational but not utopian; a country can only set the threshold to a level it would be able to provide in case every citizen chooses to realize all the ten capabilities, as listed by Nussbaum as being essential for a dignified life.

Nussbaum defines capabilities as political entitlements and hence their safeguard is the responsibility of political institutions. She argues that the responsibility of providing the central capabilities falls squarely on national governments. Given that there is no world government, she notes, it would be impossible to have the same threshold enforced by a central institution. Holding onto the concept of political liberalism, Nussbaum argues that it would be too dictatorial to oblige rich nations to transfer resources required to secure central capabilities in poor nations. This follows, therefore, poor nations should primarily set lower minimum threshold as compared to the rich nations.

Is it just, however, for an individual to have access to a lower minimum threshold of central capabilities, and consequently life of lower dignity, just by virtue of being born in a poor nation? Shouldn't the minimum threshold for a life worth of dignity be set without consideration of the resource considerations? Isn't availing different levels of human dignity according to resource endowment similar to pegging dignity to money?

In her core chapter, Nussbaum makes a number of arguments in trying to address the question of securing human dignity in poor nations. First, she states that the whole world has the obligation to secure central capabilities to all world citizens. Second, she advocates for rich nations to assist poor nations. Third, she notes that world institutions that have produced global injustices need to be changed.

Nussbaum's passing statements, nonetheless, leave more questions than answers at this stage. How should the obligation of securing central capabilities in poor nations be divided among

world actors? Should rich nations assist poor countries as a matter of philanthropy or as a given responsibility? How should the current global institutions be organized to address global injustices and how would such a change contribute to access to more resources for the poor nations? Nussbaum expounds her statements for global justice in the sixth chapter of her book.

Contrary to her earlier argument on resource transfer, she holds that rich nations ought to give poor nations at least 2% of their GDP. She continues to argue that multinational companies, non-governmental organizations, and government agencies ought to contribute to the provision of central capabilities wherever they operate. Although emphasising the importance of global institutions in solving global injustice, Nussbaum remains vague on how the change of global institutions should take place. Apart from mentioning the potential role of international institutions in imposing common norms, her arguments revolve around how states ought to intervene, or not depending on scenario, to secure central capabilities in poor nations. Nussbaum observes that the world is fluid hence making it difficult to assign permanent responsibilities and consequently unable to attain 'capability security'¹⁰. She argues that while this is a challenge, the responsibilities of world actors should be left tentative to allow for adaptation as the world community changes.

While Nussbaum has attempted to address the issue of global justice, I argue, her arguments fall short by not adequately examining the potential role of global institutions in availing resources required by poor nations to secure central capabilities. Although indeed the world community is fluid, global institutions (and particularly inter-governmental organizations) are more stable than unstable. I argue, that for the time such institutions have command over global resources, they should ensure fair distribution of such resources to poor nations.

In scrutinising the problem of global justice, Pogge examines the roles of positive and negative duties in the pursuit of global justice. When applied to the capability approach, Pogge would argue that positive duties would entail rich nations providing the means for poor countries to secure central capabilities for their citizens. Negative duties would entail rich nations ensuring that they do not hinder poor nations from achieving central capabilities. Nussbaum focuses on positive duties by arguing for transfer of a portion of GDP to poor nations, and for other world actors to assist in their various capacities towards securing central capabilities in poor nations. I argue that promoting negative duties is more important.

The current global institutions, as Nussbaum observed, result in global injustices that translate to unequal access to central capabilities hence denying poor nations the ability to secure central capabilities. These global injustices, as correctly observed by Pogge, result from global institutions which essentially serve the interests of rich nations. Since poor nations cannot exit from these institutions because of the intricate nature of globalization, they continue to suffer injustices without any significant negotiating power. It can be argued, therefore, that it is rich nations that essentially harm poor nations' ability to secure central capabilities.

Rather than focussing on transfer of resources, I argue, rich nations should apply the principle of negative duties by working towards correcting the institutions that are result in unfair distribution of global resources. For instance, rather than committing their GDP to global aid annually, rich nations should focus their efforts in the negotiation of a fair system of international trade that would give poor nations access to markets for their products. I hold that this would be a more sustainable way of securing central capabilities in poor nations; this would bring 'capability security' closer to realization.

I acknowledge that the urgency of securing the central capabilities might not be matched by the potentially slow process of negotiating a new global order. I argue for positive duties in securing the central capabilities at the minimum threshold in the short-run. Positive duties such as aid, I assert, should be conditioned first to the enforcement of functionality of the most central capabilities then to the provision of other central capabilities. This should, however, not distract the efforts of negative duties. The positive duties should incrementally be replaced by sustainable means to secure central capabilities, at least to the minimum threshold.

Reflecting back on setting of the threshold, I argue that such a decision should be made without consideration of resource availability but rather in consideration of history and way of life. I argue that if the minimum threshold is chosen without fear of resource scarcity, then the assessed threshold suffices as criteria for a life worth of dignity. A just global order, therefore, is what will ensure equal dignity for all the world citizens in the long run.

Procedural Justice

Both Rawls and Miller believe that in a just society, the principles that apply to all members of the society should be decided on through a rational process; one that is not driven by individualistic interests. It follows that the decisions made should be for the good of the society as a whole and not for the good of few individuals. In addition to rationality, both authors agree, such a process also ought to include the individuals who would be bound by the societal principles. Nussbaum's capabilities approach is rational in its logical support for the list of ten central capabilities. It, nonetheless, falls short in securing procedural justice due to its lack of inclusiveness.

Beyond the benevolent dictator

Nussbaum emphasises that the central capabilities are so essential that they should not be subject to a political process. This assertion is based on legitimate fear of negative politicization of provisions as essential as the central capabilities. However, since citizens can only be involved in societal decision making through a political process, the assertion implies exclusion of the same citizen who would be beneficiaries of such capabilities. Would it be just for individuals to be bound by universal values that they did not have a voice in choosing? What if some capabilities considered crucial for human dignity by some individuals are not guaranteed in the list of capabilities to be included in their constitution?

Throughout her book, Nussbaum supports freedom of choice and defines capabilities as individual freedoms. She also includes in her list of central capabilities, the capability of control over one's environment. Nussbaum, however, fails to take into consideration individual freedoms in the construction of her central-capabilities list. Her argument that the political goal of all humans ought to be the same, negates the individual's freedom approach that she seems to support.

The central capabilities are based on the concept of human dignity, a concept that Nussbaum argues has achieved world consensus. While this might be the case, this concept- as she rightly points out- is intuitive and vague, and needs to be assessed in relation to other concepts. It would follow, therefore, that the central capabilities are a result of such an assessment. The value system adopted by Nussbaum, she argues, is not based on people's preference but on sound argument- observed as the assessment of the concept of human dignity. It is, however, clear that only her argument was considered in the value judgment. By asserting the value of human dignity as universal, she becomes the benevolent dictator when she makes a list of capabilities that every human should be entitled to and that every society

should aspire to provide to its citizens. I argue that consensus should be the reference point in the design of the central capabilities just as it has been in establishing the paramountcy of human dignity. If the concept of human dignity has a world-wide consensus as Nussbaum asserts, I believe that the central capabilities adapted by a just society would most likely resemble Nussbaum's list.

I argue that inclusion would not only promote ownership in the definition of a life worth of dignity but it would also ensure sustainable implementation of such capabilities. Nussbaum emphasises the need to include the central capabilities in constitutions as entitlements that should be safeguarded through an inclusive political structure that allows for popular oversight. While this might be necessary for capability security, manipulation of political institutions that could impede the central capabilities would be less likely to occur if such capabilities resulted from a general agreement. Individuals, having actively participated in the decision-making process, would be keen in ensuring the implementation of their entitlements. The government would also be more willing to implement a decision they facilitated in making.

A Just Decision

In addressing the problem of how both inclusion and rationality can be achieved in decision making, I adopt the concept of social cooperation as conceived by Rawls.

Rawls argues for a conception of justice where the principles of justice are determined by fairness in decision making through social cooperation. In explaining how this social cooperation is possible in a diverse community of people, he introduces the concept of the original position. At this position, individuals forgo their biased interests and rationally negotiate to come up with a societal conception of justice. I argue that a guarantee of secured central capabilities for all in the society would allow for this rational social cooperation. Rawls argues that creating condition of fairness in the procedure empowers individuals to advance the interests of equals. Although I would advocate for a non-majoritarian democratic process- as Nussbaum envisages as a guarantee for the capabilities- I believe, a construction of such a process needs to be done in consideration of national history and traditions.

I agree with Rawls assertion that consensus on the societal values should not be fixed but should be viewed as a relative equilibrium that is adjustable. The central capabilities should, hence, be continuously examined from the original position as established through a fair process.

Conclusion

In conclusion, I would argue that Nussbaum's capability approach is indeed a partial theory of justice. The strength of the approach lies in its concept of equal dignity as equal access to the central capabilities at the minimum threshold. The approach falls short by not adequately acknowledging the role of equity in promoting social justice. In addition, by not considering the outcomes of capabilities availed to individuals, it fails to observe the potential of functionings in contradicting equal dignity. Another weakness that presents a missed opportunity is on how Nussbaum addresses global injustices.

The paper establishes that both distributive and procedural justice are important. While the capabilities approach does not adequately provide for distributive justice, as described above, it completely fails to secure procedural justice in the construction of the central capabilities.

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¹ Jost, J.T., & Kay, A.C. (2010). *Social Justice: History, Theory, and Research.* *Handbook of Social Psychology*, 3, III, 30.

² John Rawls' and David Miller's arguments were chosen for this paper because the two are contemporary political philosophers and theorists who have dedicated many years to the study the concept of justice. Although their arguments differ, their conception of justice draw from the same roots. Their theories are similar to Nussbaum's in that they also believe in central provisions that should be guaranteed in a just society.

³ Nussbaum admits that her capability approach has not addressed distribution problems above the threshold. Nussbaum, M.C. (2011, p.40)

⁴ In his capability theory, Sens argues that for one to understand people's welfare, one should not look at their income but at their ability to convert the income into welfare. He argues for an understanding of what he coined as the 'conversion factors'.

⁵ Nussbaum implies that it is common knowledge that basic capabilities are not hard-wired in the DNA. Nussbaum, M.C. (2011, p.23)

⁶ The logic behind the terminology 'negative equity' derives from its effect; it prevents disadvantages from negatively affecting the ability to enjoy combined capabilities.

⁷ 'Positive equity' has the opposite effect of 'negative equity'; it enhances the enjoyment of capabilities for those with advantages.

⁸ 'Elite' has been used to connote individuals with superior capabilities, and not necessarily those enjoying financial abundance.

⁹ 'Capability gap' as used in this paper refers to difference in available capabilities at the minimum threshold and the capabilities enjoyed by the elites.

¹⁰ 'Capability security' as described by Nussbaum is the assurance of future availability of the central capabilities.